

Toda

Data source: eHRAF

Secondary source

Entered by Emily Pitek, Human Relations Area Files

** Data Source entry, prepared based on data sourced from an external project.*

** Secondary Source entry, prepared from a literature review by a Ph.D. RA*

Entry tags: Indic Religious Traditions, Religious Group

The Toda historically inhabited the Nilgiri Mountains of southern India; this entry focuses around the time of 1900. At this time, the Toda had been in contact with Europeans, and India was under British rule. However, according to the principal ethnographic authority William Rivers (1906) European influence had minimal effect on Toda religious beliefs and activities. The Toda social structure included two endogamous divisions: the Teivaliol and Tartharol, each with several subdivisions (clans). Political leadership was maintained by the naim; a governing council composed of five individuals from various clans. The naim also held functions in connection with religious activities, deciding when ceremonies would take place and regulating the ti (sacred buffalo and accompanying dairies and grazing lands). As a pastoralist society, the Toda relied heavily on their cattle and dairies. The cattle played a significant role in the daily aspects of life (e.g., subsistence, economic), and also featured prominently in religious beliefs and practices. Certain buffalo are considered sacred and are associated with sacred dairies, ceremonies, and are tended to by dairymen-priests. Organized in a hierarchical manner, each level of dairy had its own grade of ritual and priesthood, with an increasing need for ritual purity and elaborateness of rituals for daily tasks. The ti comprises the most sacred level and is maintained by the palol (dairyman-priest, religious practitioner) who is selected from the Teivaliol division. The main types of Toda religious ceremonies are those associated with the dairy and those accompanying life-cycle events. Because the Toda religion permeates almost all aspects of life, this entry considers the religious group to be coterminous with Toda society itself.

Date Range: 1885 CE - 1910 CE

Region: Nilgiri Hills, western Tamil Nadu state, India

Region tags: India

Nilgiri Hills, western Tamil Nadu state, India ca. 1900

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Murdock, G.P. (1967). *Ethnographic Atlas*. Pittsburgh, PA: University of Pittsburgh Press.
- Source 1: Divale, W. (2004). Codebook of Variables for the Standard Cross-Cultural Sample. *World Cultures: The Journal of Cross-Cultural and Comparative Research*.
- Source 2: Murdock, G.P. & Wilson, S.F. (Jul., 1972). Settlement patterns and community organization: *Cross-Cultural Codes 3. Ethnology*, 11(3), 254-295.
- Source 3: Tuden, A. & Marshall, C. (Oct., 1972). Political organization: *Cross-cultural codes 4. Ethnology*, 11(4), 436-464.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=aw60-001>

– Source 1 Description: Rivers, W. H. R. (William H. R. (1906). *The Todas*. Macmillan.

– Source 2 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=aw60-000>

– Source 2 Description: Walker, A. R. (2010). Culture summary: Toda. Human Relations Area Files.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: "The hills were visited by a Portuguese missionary in 1602, and have been invaded by Indian tribes on various occasions, but, at the beginning of the last century, the plateau and its inhabitants were absolutely unknown to Europeans" (Rivers, 1906:1). "Among the Todas missionary influence, whether of Christian or Hindu, has had little effect, and the ritual of the Todas in some parts of the hills is almost, if not quite, untouched by outside influences" (Rivers, 1906:4). "The Todas show undoubted signs of the influence of Hinduism on their religion" (Rivers, 1906:457). "This worship and appeal to Hindu deities appears to me to have gone on side by side with the proper religion of the Todas, but to have influenced it little" (Rivers, 1906:458).

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 1649 (Frequency of Internal Warfare, Resolved Rating), "internal warfare seems to be absent or rare" (Ember and Ember, 1992; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 1650 (Frequency of External Warfare, Resolved Rating), "external warfare seems to be absent or rare" (Ember and Ember, 1992; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating the Toda would actively proselytize and recruit new members.

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: "In addition to its functions in disputes between individuals, the naim [governing council] has

wide functions in connection with Toda ceremonial. It decides when many ceremonies take place, and has the chief word in regulating the affairs of the ti [sacred] dairies. Thus it appeared that the various arrangements and alterations of arrangements in connexion with the migration of the buffaloes of the Nodrs ti which were made during my visit were the work of the naim, or, at any rate, of its chief members" (Rivers, 1906:553).

Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– No

Notes: A council of five individuals maintains political leadership; there does not appear to be a formal head of the polity. See Rivers (1906:550) for more details.

Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– No

Notes: "Another point about which several writers have erred is in supposing that the palol [dairyman-priest, religious practitioner] is important in the general government of the Todas and in stating that the Todas go to him for counsel and advice. I inquired into this very carefully, and there seemed to be no doubt whatever that the palol has absolutely no functions outside the management of his dairy and of ceremonies connected with it" (Rivers, 1906:101).

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating the presence of a conception of apostasy.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 736

Notes: "If the number of the Todas now living and recorded in the genealogies be counted, it will be found that there are 736 individuals, 419 males and 317 females" (Rivers, 1906:469).

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "The ti is the name of an institution which comprises a herd of buffaloes with a number of dairies and grazing districts tended by a dairyman-priest or priests called palol with an assistant called kaltmokh. Each dairy with its accompanying buildings and pasturage is called a ti mad, or ti village" (Rivers, 1906:83). "Dairies, which Toda themselves identify as temples, are buildings kept in a state of ritual purity so that dairymen-priests (of comparable ritual purity) can process inside them the milk from associated herds of sacred buffalo. Ranked in a hierarchy, each grade of dairy has its associated grade of sacred buffalo and dairyman-priest. The higher the grade of a dairy, the greater is the need for ritual purity and the more elaborate the rituals that surround the daily tasks of the dairyman" (Walker, 2010:9).

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

Notes: "Dairies, which Toda themselves identify as temples, are buildings kept in a state of ritual purity so that dairymen-priests (of comparable ritual purity) can process inside them the milk from associated herds of sacred buffalo. Ranked in a hierarchy, each grade of dairy has its associated grade of sacred buffalo and dairyman-priest. The higher the grade of a dairy, the greater is the need for ritual purity and the more elaborate the rituals that surround the daily tasks of the dairyman" (Walker, 2010:9).

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– Yes

Notes: "The sanctity attaching to the palol and the reverence paid to him are attached and paid wholly to the holder of the office and not at all to the man" (Rivers, 1906:101).

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from a supernatural being:

– No

Notes: "The sanctity attaching to the palol and the reverence paid to him are attached and paid wholly to the holder of the office and not at all to the man" (Rivers, 1906:101).

↳ Powers are associated with leadership office they assume:

– Yes

Notes: "The sanctity attaching to the palol and the reverence paid to him are attached and paid wholly to the holder of the office and not at all to the man" (Rivers, 1906:101).

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– Yes

Notes: "The palol, who must belong to the Teivaliol [one of the two sub-divisions of the Toda], is chosen by the members of the Tarthar [the other sub-division] clan to which the ti [sacred dairy] belongs" (Rivers, 1906:98).

↳ Other members of the leader's congregation choose the leader:

– Yes

Notes: "The palol, who must belong to the Teivaliol [one of the two sub-divisions of the Toda], is chosen by the members of the Tarthar [the other sub-division] clan to which the ti [sacred dairy] belongs" (Rivers, 1906:98).

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral

scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating the presence of scripture.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Notes: Presumably, monumental religious architecture is absent; according to Murdock and Wilson (1972, Column 6: Large or Impressive Structures), "there are no structures in the community that are appreciably larger or more impressive than the usual residential dwellings."

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

Notes: "The milking and churning operations of the dairy form the basis of the greater part of the religious ritual of the Todas. The lives of the people are largely devoted to their buffaloes, and the care of certain of these animals, regarded as more sacred than the rest, is associated with much ceremonial. The sacred animals are attended by men especially set apart who form the Toda priesthood, and the milk of the sacred animals is churned in dairies which may be regarded as the Toda temples and are so regarded by the people themselves. The ordinary operations of the dairy have become a religious ritual and ceremonies of a religious character accompany nearly every important incident in the lives of the buffaloes" (Rivers, 1906:38).

Tombs:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating the presence of tombs. Additionally, the bodies of the deceased are cremated, not entombed. For a description of Toda funerary practices see Rivers (1906, pp. 361-365)

Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes [specify]: Dairies

Notes: "Dairies, which Toda themselves identify as temples, are buildings kept in a state of ritual purity so that dairymen-priests (of comparable ritual purity) can process inside them the milk from associated herds of sacred buffalo. Ranked in a hierarchy, each grade of dairy has its associated grade of sacred buffalo and dairyman-priest. The higher the grade of a dairy, the greater is the need for ritual purity and the more elaborate the rituals that surround the daily tasks of the dairyman" (Walker, 2010:9).

Is iconography present:

– I don't know

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Notes: "[Nòtirz, a female deity] is the nòdrodchi of the two important clans of Melgars and Kuudr, and lives on the hill now known as Snowdon, the Toda name of the hill being the same as that of the goddess. This hill is especially sacred, and any Toda who visits it has to salute with hand to forehead (kaimukhti) in all directions" (Rivers, 1906:189).

Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Notes: "[Nòtirz, a female deity] is the nòdrodchi of the two important clans of Melgars and Kuudr, and lives on the hill now known as Snowdon, the Toda name of the hill being the same as that of the goddess. This hill is especially sacred, and any Toda who visits it has to salute with hand to forehead (kaimukhti) in all directions" (Rivers, 1906:189).

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: "Amnòdr is the other world of the Todas to which the dead go. It lies to the west and is lighted by the same sun as this world" (Rivers, 1906:397). "Amnòdr is presided over by the god Òn, who went there after the death of his son Püv, and it is often called Önnòdr after him, while this world, presided over by the goddess Teikirzi, is known as Inanòdr or Eikirzinòdr. The people of Amnòdr or Önnòdr are known as the Amatol" (ibid, p.398).

Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– I don't know

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: "Amnòdr is the other world of the Todas to which the dead go. It lies to the west and is lighted by the same sun as this world" (Rivers, 1906:397).

Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "Amnòdr is the other world of the Todas to which the dead go. It lies to the west and is

lighted by the same sun as this world...Amnòdr is considered to be below this world, and this was given as the reason why the dead used to be burnt face downwards" (Rivers, 1906:397).

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space:

– No

Notes: "Amnòdr is the other world of the Todas to which the dead go. It lies to the west and is lighted by the same sun as this world...Amnòdr is considered to be below this world, and this was given as the reason why the dead used to be burnt face downwards" (Rivers, 1906:397).

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space:

– Yes

Notes: "Amnòdr is the other world of the Todas to which the dead go. It lies to the west and is lighted by the same sun as this world...Amnòdr is considered to be below this world, and this was given as the reason why the dead used to be burnt face downwards" (Rivers, 1906:397).

Reincarnation in this world:

– Yes

Notes: "The Amatol [the dead] live in much the same way as the inhabitants of this world. They have their buffaloes and their dairies, and the daily life of the people appears to be much like that of the living Todas. As the people walk about, however, they wear down their legs. They have to walk every day, and when a man has worn down his legs as far as the knees Ön [a deity] sends him back to this world as another man" (Rivers, 1906:398).

↳ In a human form:

– Yes

Notes: "The Amatol [the dead] live in much the same way as the inhabitants of this world. They have their buffaloes and their dairies, and the daily life of the people appears to be much like that of the living Todas. As the people walk about, however, they wear down their legs. They have to walk every day, and when a man has worn down his legs as far as the knees Ön [a deity] sends him back to this world as another man" (Rivers, 1906:398).

↳ In animal/plant form:

– No

Notes: Reincarnation is only described to occur in human form.

↳ In form of an inanimate object(s):

– No

Notes: Reincarnation is only described to occur in human form.

↳ Reincarnation linked to notion of life-transcending causality (e.g. karma):

– No

Notes: Reincarnation does not appear to be linked to a notion of life-transcending causality. Rather, reincarnation is said to occur after spirits have been in the afterworld for some time. "The Amatol [the dead] live in much the same way as the inhabitants of this world. They have their buffaloes and their dairies, and the daily life of the people appears to be much like that of the living Todas. As the people walk about, however, they wear down their legs. They have to walk every day, and when a man has worn down his legs as far as the knees Öñ [a deity] sends him back to this world as another man" (Rivers, 1906:398).

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: "Soon after death the body is burnt and the general name for the ceremony on this occasion is *etvainokedr*, the first day funeral (literally, 'first which day funeral')" (Rivers, 1906:337). For a complete description of cremation ceremonies, see Rivers (1906, pp. 361-365). "Customarily two funeral rites were held and it was believed that the deceased could not enter the Land of the Dead until the second was complete. At the first funeral, the body was cremated; at the second, a relic (lock of hair or fragment of bone) was burned" (Walker, 2010: 11).

↳ Cremation:

– Yes

Notes: "Soon after death the body is burnt and the general name for the ceremony on this occasion is *etvainokedr*, the first day funeral (literally, 'first which day funeral')" (Rivers, 1906:337). For a complete description of cremation ceremonies, see Rivers (1906, pp. 361-365).

↳ Mummification:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating the presence of mummification.

↳ Interment:

– No

Notes: "Soon after death the body is burnt and the general name for the ceremony on this occasion is *etvainokedr*, the first day funeral (literally, 'first which day funeral')" (Rivers, 1906:337).

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating the presence of cannibalism.

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating the presence of feeding corpses to animals.

↳ Secondary burial:

– Yes

Notes: "Customarily two funeral rites were held and it was believed that the deceased could not enter the Land of the Dead until the second was complete. At the first funeral, the body was cremated; at the second, a relic (lock of hair or fragment of bone) was burned" (Walker, 2010:11). According to SCCS Variable 1850: Secondary bone/body treatment (original scale), "secondary contact with the body or bones is the preferred means of disposal for all or nearly all adult members of the society" (Schroeder, 2001; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: Co-sacrifices are not present at burials because the deceased are cremated, not buried. However, one aspect of funeral rites involves slaughtering buffalo. "At the present time the Todas are only permitted by the Government to kill two of these animals, and if the family of the dead person is poor only one may be killed. At the funeral of a man it is customary that one of the animals killed shall be an ordinary buffalo (putiir) and the other a sacred buffalo.... At least one sacred buffalo must be killed at one or other funeral ceremony for every man, but this may be done either at the etvainol- or the marvainolkedr. Sacred buffaloes are only killed at the funerals of men, never at those of women" (Rivers, 1906:349).

Are grave goods present:

– No

Notes: Grave goods cannot be said to be present because the deceased are cremated, not buried. However, goods are burned with the body during cremation, and objects of value may be removed from the pyre and redistributed before cremation. "The bier is laid by the side of the pyre, and the dead person is then supplied with the various necessaries for the other world. Many of the things are placed in the large pocket, or kudsh, between the two folds of the cloak in which the body is enclosed. The things supplied are chiefly food, ornaments, and money. The food includes grain, rice, jaggery, limes, and honey. Some of the food is put directly into the kudsh, while some of the grain, rice, and honey are mixed together and put in a metal bowl. Tobacco, coconuts, ghi, or articles of food from the bazaar may be added" (Rivers, 1906:361).

Are formal burials present:

– No

Notes: Formal burials are not present. However, formal funerals and many associated ceremonies, including cremation, are present. For a complete description of Toda funerary practices, see Rivers (1906, pp. 337-397). "Customarily two funeral rites were held and it was believed that the deceased could not enter the Land of the Dead until the second was complete. At the first funeral, the body was cremated; at the second, a relic (lock of hair or fragment of bone) was burned" (Walker, 2010: 11).

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: "Each clan of the Todas has a deity especially connected with it. This deity is called the nòdrodchi of the clan, and is believed to have been the ruler of the clan when gods and men lived together" (Rivers, 1906:183). "There was no doubt that two gods stood out pre-eminent among the rest. One was a male deity whose name was Öñ, and the other a female deity, Teikirzi. A simple question which I had the greatest difficulty in settling was the relation of these deities to one another" (Rivers, 1906:183).

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 238, High Gods (Note, Equivalent to Ethnographic Atlas Column 34:High Gods), a high god is absent or not reported (Murdock, 1967; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: Previously human spirits are present, but not described in significant detail. "Amnòdr is the other world of the Todas to which the dead go. It lies to the west and is lighted by the same sun as this world" (Rivers, 1906:397). "Amnòdr is presided over by the god Öñ, who went there after the death of his son Püv, and it is often called Önnòdr after him, while this world, presided over by the goddess Teikirzi, is known as Inanòdr or Eikirzinòdr. The people of Amnòdr or Önnòdr are known as the Amatol" (ibid, p.398).

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: One Toda ceremony, called tersamtpini, is "performed together with or later than the ceremony of name-giving when a child is about three months old. The chief feature of the ceremony is that a lock of the child's hair is cut by the maternal uncle of the child, the hair of a Tarthar [clan] child being cut with a piece of sharpened iron called kanab, while the hair of a Teivali [clan] child is cut with an ordinary knife. The special interest, however, for our present purpose lies in the fact that this ceremony must be performed on the day after the second funeral of a Tarthar man, and this whether the child be Tarthar or Teivali. This ceremony points to the existence of a belief in the influence of the spirit of the dead man, and I have already (p. 404) given reasons why it is probable that this influence should be regarded as good rather than bad" (Rivers, 1906:685).

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: "Each clan of the Todas has a deity especially connected with it. This deity is called the nõdrodchi of the clan, and is believed to have been the ruler of the clan when gods and men lived together" (Rivers, 1906:183). "There was no doubt that two gods stood out pre-eminent among the rest. One was a male deity whose name was Öñ, and the other a female deity, Teikirzi. A simple question which I had the greatest difficulty in settling was the relation of these deities to one another" (Rivers, 1906:183).

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– No

Notes: "At the present time none of the gods are ever seen by mortals" (Rivers, 1906:451).

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: "...an offense against the dairy was punished by the gods" (Rivers, 1906:427).

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

Notes: "...an offense against the dairy was punished by the gods" (Rivers, 1906:427).

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: "Although the Toda deities seem to be in general a development of hill-spirits, there can be little doubt that some of the gods are deified men. In the case of Kwoten, the account of his life is so circumstantial as to leave little doubt that he was a real man who was deified after a mysterious disappearance, believed to have been due to intercourse with a female deity, and around whose life there have clustered certain miraculous incidents" (Rivers, 1906:446).

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be seen:

– I don't know

↳ These mixed human-divine beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– I don't know

↳ These mixed human-divine beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– I don't know

↳ Mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living:

– I don't know

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: "The earliest of the gods was Pithi, who was born in a cave, and the Todas and many of their buffaloes were created by his son Öñ and his wife. Later death came to the gods in the person of Püv, the son of Öñ and Öñ followed Püv to the world of the dead, called Amnòdr, of which he has since been the ruler. He left behind him as predominant among the deities Teikirzi, a goddess, who ruled over the Todas" (Rivers, 1906:443). "There seem to have been many other gods contemporaneous with Öñ and Teikirzi, and certain of these are believed to have been related to these deities and especially to Teikirzi. The gods are believed to be very numerous: the Todas speak of the 1,600 gods, the 1,800 gods, but it would seem that these expressions are used in the sense of 'an infinite number'" (ibid).

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– Yes

Notes: See Rivers, 1906:443

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural monitoring is clearly present, evidenced by the following quote: "...the gods are held to be the source of punishment for sins committed by the Todas, and that they may be appeased by offerings" (Rivers, 1906:449). However, the specific sins that warrant supernatural punishment are not described, other than sins against the dairy, or non-adherence to proper rituals (see Rivers, 1906:449).

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

Notes: "In several cases dairies have been disused because the dairymen have died in office, and this was said to have happened because the gods of those places were severe. It was apparently believed that they had visited infringements of the laws regulating dairy ritual with death" (Rivers, 1906:449).

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

Notes: "In several cases dairies have been disused because the dairymen have died in office, and this was said to have happened because the gods of those places were severe. It was apparently believed that they had visited infringements of the laws regulating dairy ritual with death" (Rivers, 1906:449).

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Notes: "...the gods are held to be the source of punishment for sins committed by the Todas, and that they may be appeased by offerings" (Rivers, 1906:449).

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: See questions below for more information regarding the cause of supernatural punishments.

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 238, High Gods (Note, Equivalent to Ethnographic Atlas Column 34:High Gods), a high god is absent or not reported (Murdock, 1967; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: "...when a clan or a member of a clan is said to incur the anger of the gods it is the nõdrodchi [ruling deity, of a clan] who is chiefly offended and inflicts punishment in the form of death or disease to man or buffalo" (Rivers, 1906:449).

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

Notes: "The diviners usually work in pairs, though occasionally it would seem that one only may be consulted. If they are asked for an explanation of some misfortune which has befallen a man, the teuol usually find either that the sufferer has committed an offence against the dairy or that he is the subject of spells cast on him by a sorcerer. In

the former case, they prescribe the ceremony which must be performed in order to expiate the offence" (Rivers, 1906:252).

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: See questions below for more information regarding reasons for supernatural punishment.

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

Notes: "In several cases dairies have been disused because the dairymen have died in office, and this was said to have happened because the gods of those places were severe. It was apparently believed that they had visited infringements of the laws regulating dairy ritual with death" (Rivers, 1906:449).

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: "On proceeding [to the land of the dead, Amnòdr] the dead Todas come to a ravine and river called Püvürkin, near Sisapara. Across this river there is a thread bridge, and those who have been bad Todas during life fall into the river and are bitten by leeches (püv or püf). The people who cross the thread bridge successfully go straight to Amnòdr, but those who fall are helped out of the river by the people of Padrmukhteir (crowd plain swamp), who belong to all tribes and live on the further bank of Püvürkin. The people of Padrmukhteir may keep the offending Todas in their country for some time. The greater their offences, the longer are they kept, but all, however bad, reach Amnòdr sooner or later" (Rivers, 1906:399).

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– No

Notes: Punishment in the afterlife consists of delayed arrival to the afterworld (see Rivers, 1906:399). No evidence indicating that punishment consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– No

Notes: Punishment in the afterlife consists of delayed arrival to the afterworld (see Rivers, 1906:399). No evidence indicating that punishment consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm.

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Punishment in the afterlife consists of delayed arrival to the afterworld (see Rivers, 1906:399).

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Notes: "...when a clan or a member of a clan is said to incur the anger of the gods it is the nõdrodchi [ruling deity, of a clan] who is chiefly offended and inflicts punishment in the form of death or disease to man or buffalo" (Rivers, 1906:449).

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

Notes: "...when a clan or a member of a clan is said to incur the anger of the gods it is the nõdrodchi [ruling deity, of a clan] who is chiefly offended and inflicts punishment in the form of death or disease to man or buffalo" (Rivers, 1906:449).

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Death. "...when a clan or a member of a clan is said to incur the anger of the gods it is the nõdrodchi [ruling deity, of a clan] who is chiefly offended and inflicts punishment in the form of death or disease to man or buffalo" (Rivers, 1906:449).

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– I don't know

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating the presence of messianic beliefs.

Norms and Moral Realism

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "Again, we have seen that the Todas have a code of offences against the dairy, but these must be regarded as sins rather than as crimes, for they are neither investigated nor punished by the civil authority, the naim [government council], but are punished directly by the gods, and the various ceremonies described in Chapter XIII are expiatory and not punitive" (Rivers, 1906:554).

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Present and clear

Notes: "Again, we have seen that the Todas have a code of offences against the dairy, but these must be regarded as sins rather than as crimes, for they are neither investigated nor punished by the civil authority, the naim [government council], but are punished directly by the gods,

and the various ceremonies described in Chapter XIII are expiatory and not punitive" (Rivers, 1906:554).

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– Yes

Notes: "The palol [dairyman-priest] must be celibate, and if married, he must leave his wife, who is in most cases also the wife of his brother or brothers" (Rivers, 1906:99).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: "From the foregoing account it appears that a woman may have one or more recognised lovers as well as several husbands... Further, there seems to be no doubt that there is little restriction of any kind on sexual intercourse. I was assured by several Todas not only that adultery was no motive for divorce, but that it was in no way regarded as wrong. It seemed clear that there is no word for adultery in the Toda language" (Rivers, 1906:529).

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating the presence of castration.

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– I don't know

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– I don't know

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– I don't know

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: "In the ti [sacred] dairy, prayer is offered both morning and evening; at the morning ceremonial twice and in the afternoon three times. On both occasions the first prayer begins when the lamp is being lighted and is continued while the palol [dayman-priest] knocks on one of the persin with the persinkudriki. The second prayer in each case is offered at the conclusion of the milking, and the third prayer of the afternoon corresponds to the second prayer of the village dairy, being offered when shutting up the buffaloes for the night" (Rivers, 1906:235).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

Notes: A variety of rituals and ceremonies occur in relation to the sacred buffalos and their dairy, as well as the dairymen-priests. "Ranked in a hierarchy, each grade of dairy has its associated grade of sacred buffalo and dairyman-priest. The higher the grade of a dairy, the greater is the need for ritual purity and the more elaborate the rituals that surround the daily tasks of the dairyman" (Walker, 2010:9). Ceremonies involve activities such as converting milk into other substances (e.g., butter), migration of the herds, and officiating dairymen into office (see Rivers, 1906:231). Additionally, "there remain ceremonies which accompany certain events in the course of the dairy ritual or in the lives of the buffaloes. One of these, the pepkaricha ceremony, is performed whenever any evil befalls a certain dairy vessel which is buried in the buffalo pen. Another ceremony celebrates the birth of a calf, and a group of ceremonies are connected with the act of giving salt to the buffaloes" (Rivers, 1906:166). These rituals have a religious significance and are led by the dairymen. However, it appears that not all members of society participate in such rituals.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

- ↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):
Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.
– I don't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:
I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."
– I don't know

Notes: The two main categories of Toda ceremonies include those associated with the dairy and life-cycle events (birth, adolescence, funeral). Although important, it is unclear whether these ceremonies are large-scale. Toda ceremonies are described in detail throughout Rivers (1906).

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

Notes: See questions below for more details regarding extra-ritual in-group markers.

↳ Other:

– Yes [specify]: Ear piercing

Notes: "Only the ears of boys are pierced, and a boy may not enter upon the more sacred offices of the dairy till this ceremony has been performed" (Rivers, 1906:335).

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A chiefdom

Notes: The Toda had one level of jurisdictional hierarchy beyond the local community, which is indicative of a petty chiefdom (Ethnographic Atlas column 33, Murdock, 1967).

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– I don't know

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: "In 1799 the mountains became a British possession, though unadministered until after 1819. Before that time, Toda may have paid a grazing tax to overlords in the plains, but their physical isolation atop the high Nilgiris permitted a way of life mostly untrammled by outside interference. After the assertion of British rule, Toda were never again to be quite free of state bureaucracy" (Walker, 2010:2).

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 20: Food Storage, food was stored in individual households (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 20: Food Storage, food was stored in individual households (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 14: Routes of Land Transport, the Toda utilized unimproved trails (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; Retrieved from Divale, 2004). Presumably, transportation infrastructure was not present.

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 14: Routes of Land Transport, the Toda utilized unimproved trails (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; Retrieved from Divale, 2004). Presumably, transportation infrastructure was not present.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Notes: Tuden and Marshall (1972) column 10, Police (note, equivalent to SCCS variable 90, Police) indicates that "police functions are not specialized or institutionalized at any level of political integration, the maintenance of law and order being left exclusively to informal mechanisms of social control, to private retaliation, or to sorcery."

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 149, Scale 1-Writing and Records, the Toda did not possess writing and records (Murdock and Provost, 1971; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: "The Todas have twelve months, each of which begins with the new moon. The first month of the Toda year is Tai, which begins with the new moon in October, so that this month usually includes part of October and part of November" (Rivers, 1906:590). For additional information on the Toda calendar, see Rivers (1906, pp.590-592).

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: "The Todas are a purely pastoral people, limiting their activities almost entirely to the care of their buffaloes and to the complicated ritual which has grown up in association with these animals" (Rivers, 1906:6). The Todas rely primarily on animal husbandry; gathering supplements the diet. Source of information from Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1962-1971), retrieved from Divale, 2004; Variables 203-207, 232.

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Gathering

– Pastoralism

Notes: "The Todas are a purely pastoral people, limiting their activities almost entirely to the care of their buffaloes and to the complicated ritual which has grown up in association with these animals" (Rivers, 1906:6). The Todas rely primarily on animal husbandry; gathering supplements the diet. Source of information from Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1962-1971), retrieved from Divale, 2004; Variables 203-207, 232.